

AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF VATASHTHILA W.S.R. TO BENIGN PROSTATIC HYPERPLASIA: A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

A severe urinary condition called benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH) is a senile illness that usually affects men over the age of 50, characterized by urinary incontinence, incomplete voiding, dribbling, and retention of urine. Benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH) is mentioned in Ayurvedic texts as Vatashtila (i.e., it is one of the types of Mutraghata in which there is decreased urine flow due to obstruction in the urinary passage). In contemporary science conservative and surgical treatment are given to the patients suffering with BPH. A male patient (52 years) want Ayurvedic treatment, came with symptoms Frequent urination, Nocturia, Hesitancy, Urgency, Retention of urine since 2 months.^[8] Trivanga bhasma, Kachnaar guggul, Ural BPH capsules (vasu) were given to the patient along with following Pathya Apathya. These medicines improved the tonicity of urinary bladder and reduce the size of the prostate.

KEYWORDS: Vatashtila, Benign prostatic hyperplasia, Ayurvedic Management.

INTRODUCTION

BPH is a non-malignant enlargement of the prostate caused by cellular hyperplasia.^[1] BPH is an ailment commonly encountered in old aged males.^[2] BPH affects both glandular epithelium and connective tissue stroma.^[3] Incidence of BPH increases by 122% from 1990 to 2021. BPH rate is 25% in 40-49 age group, rising to 37% in 50-59 and 60-69 age groups, 50% in 70-79 age group.^[4] In India total number of BPH cases increased by 90.9% between 2000-2019 from approximately 9.55 million to 18.2 million.^[5] It includes obstructive and

irritative urinary symptoms like urinary retention, dribbling of urine, burning micturition. The main symptoms of BPH are increased nocturnal frequency (5-10 times during the night) followed by day and night due to ineffective emptying of the bladder, urgency (urgent desire to pass urine), hesitancy (difficulty in initiating the urinary stream), pain due to cystitis in suprapubic and loin region.^[6] Acharya Sushruta has mentioned various etiological factors like suppression of natural urges (i.e.; Vegavarodha), excessive exercise (i.e.; Ativyayam), excessive sexual intercourse (i.e.; Ativyavya), excess intake of astringent, bitter, and pungent foods (i.e.; Katu and Teekshna Rasa Ahara), excess use of wine and fleshy meat leads to Vatasthila (i.e.; BPH). Above mentioned causative factors leads to vitiation of Vata Dosha that are mainly involved in the pathogenesis of benign prostatic hyperplasia.^[7] Presence of vitiated Vata along with Kapha and Pitta undergoes process of cellular proliferation. The action of vitiated Vata over fibrous part, results into hardening of tissues. So to break the Samprapti of disease, Ayurvedic medicines were chosen to treat the present case.

CASE STUDY

On 22/11/2024, a 52 years old male patient came to the OPD for Ayurvedic treatment with chief complaints of increased frequency of urination especially at night (nocturia), Frequent urination, Hesitancy, Urgency to pass urine, Retention of urine, weak urine stream since 2 months. The patient has no significant past history of any chronic disease, trauma or surgical interventions. No family history is seen. Ultrasonography showed Grade 1 prostatomegaly.

Vitals: BP- 140/90 mmHg, Pulse Rate - 74/min, RR- 18/Min, Weight- 82 kg.

Treatment Protocol

1. Kachnaar guggul 500 mg 2 tab BD for 3 months with luke warm water after meals.
2. Trivanga bhasma 125 mg BD for 3 months with honey before meals.
3. Ural BPH capsules (Vasu) 1 cap BD for 3 months with luke warm water after meals.

Pathya-Apathya

Food containing Madhura, Lavana, Amla Rasa, Plant based diet, fruits containing beta carotene and vitamin C, Vegetables like tomato, garlic and onion was advised. Vata dosha aggravating food containing Tikta, Kashaya, Katu Rasa, red meat, fat, alcohol, caffeine, high protein diet was restricted.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

Subjective parameters

Sign and symptoms were assessed by International Prostate symptom score (IPPS):

Sign and symptoms	Not at all	Almost never	A few times	Sometimes	Most times	Almost always
Incomplete Emptying	0	1	2	3	4	5
Frequency	0	1	2	3	4	5
Intermittency	0	1	2	3	4	5
Urgency	0	1	2	3	4	5
Weak stream	0	1	2	3	4	5
Straining	0	1	2	3	4	5
Nocturia	0 (never)	1 time	2 times	3 times	4 times	5 times

Objective parameters: Ultrasonography was done before and after treatment.

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Subjective parameters

Sign and symptoms	B.T.	A.T.
Incomplete Emptying	3	0
Frequency	4	1
Intermittency	1	0
Urgency	2	0
Weak stream	2	0
Straining	0	0
Nocturia	4 times	1 time

Objective parameters

Before treatment Ultrasonography showed Grade 1 Prostatomegaly.

After treatment Ultrasonography showed Normal size.

DISCUSSION

BPH is common health problem in geriatric age group these days. According to Ayurveda, the vitiated Apana Vata and Kapha Dushti causes Sthira, Unnata (elevated) Astheelavata (stone-like growth), occupies the region between the rectum and the urinary bladder This growth causes obstructions to the passage of urine, flatus, and faeces, resulting in suprapubic discomfort. This condition is linked to the symptoms of BPH. To break this pathology and to combat sign and symptoms Kachnaar Guggul, Trivang Bhasma, Ural BPH capsules were chosen. Kachnaar Guggul due to its Tikta, Kshaya Rasa, Laghu and Ruksha Guna, it subsides aggravated Kapha dosha. Ushana Virya causes Vata and Kapha dosha to diminish.^[8] Its

specific indication is in Gandamala, a severe form of Apache, Arbuda, Granthi, Vrana, Gulma, Kushtha and Bhagandara.^[9] BPH is also a type of Granthi. The overall pathological phenomenon of BPH also shows the same kind of fibrotic growth in prostatic parenchyma. Trivang Bhasma contain Yashada (Zinc) which plays crucial role in regulating testosterone levels and inhibits conversion of testosterone to dihydrotestosterone (DHT), a hormone linked to prostate enlargement. Zinc helps prevent excessive cell proliferation, which can lead to BPH. Zinc has anti-inflammatory properties and vital for healthy immune response which manage prostatitis and prevent infections.^[10] Vanga (Tin) is Laghu, Ruksha, Tikta, Kashaya, Lavana Rasa and Naaga (Lead) has Snigdha, Ushna, Guru, Sara, Ushna Virya which pacifies Vata Kapha Doshas. Ural BPH capsules contain Varuna, Punarnavadi kwath, Chandraprabha vati as chief ingredients. Varuna, due to its triterpene content, can improve the tone of the detrusor or the musculature of the urinary bladder which reduces residual urine volume, blocks alpha receptor and relaxes smooth muscles of prostate and it has anti-infective qualities.^[11] Punarnava has Tikta Rasa, Ushna Virya, Ruksha Guna which pacifies Kapha Dosh.^[12] Chandraprabha Vati assists in treating problems related to the male and female reproductive system and various urinary tract disorders (UTI), bladder related issues. It also helps to remove kidney stones by increasing the production of urine due to its diuretic activity.^[13] It has Mutrikrichanashak and Mutraghatanashak properties. It exhibits anti-inflammatory effects by inhibiting cyclooxygenase (COX) and prostaglandin pathways, specifically in BPH.^[14] The combination of these three medicines showed significant improvement in sign and symptoms of BPH.

CONCLUSION

Improvements were seen in sign and symptoms of BPH after 3 months of treatment. Ultrasonography showed positive outcomes from Grade 1 prostatomegaly to normal in size after treatment. Hence, it is observed that combination of Kachnaar guggul, Trivanga bhasma, Ural BPH capsules showed synergetic effect on hormonal and physiological levels as a result of their antiandrogenic, antiinflammatory, anti-biotic, anti-mutagenic, antispasmodic, anti-fibroblastic and other growth factor properties in treating BPH disease.

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